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Review Article

**PHYTOSOMES AS INNOVATIVE DELIVERY SYSTEMS FOR
PHYTOCHEMICALS: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW****Sasikanth Kothamasu*¹, Birudugadda Sindhuja², B. Thangabalan¹**

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Article Received: October 2024 Accepted: November 2024 Published: December 2024**Abstract:**

Phytoconstituents have been used in medicine since ancient times due to their various pharmacological actions. In spite of having excellent bio-activity of plant extract and their phytoconstituents in vitro they have no in vivo actions due to their poor lipid solubility or inappropriate molecular size or both, which results in their poor absorption and lower bioavailability. Phytosomes are the novel formulation technology which helps to overcome these problems. Phytosomes are produced by a process whereby a standardized plant extract or its constituents are bound to phospholipids; mainly phosphatidylcholine, producing a lipid compatible complex. The phytosome technology has been applied over many popular herbal drugs such as Ginkgo biloba, hawthorn, olive oil, grape seed, green tea and ginseng. This article reviews the recent trends in phytosomes drug delivery.

Keywords: *Phytosomes, Bioavailability, Plant Extract, Drug Delivery, Phytoconstituents***Corresponding author:****Sasikanth Kothamasu,**

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INTRODUCTION:

The word phytosomes is derived from term "phyto" which means plant while "some" means cell like. Phytosome is a patented technology developed by a leading manufacturer of drugs and nutraceuticals, to incorporate standardized plant extracts or water soluble phyto-constituents into phospholipids to produce lipid compatible molecular complexes, called as phytosomes and this vastly improve their absorption and bioavailability. Phytosomes are novel drug delivery system containing hydrophilic bioactive phytoconstituents of herbs surround and bound by phospholipids. Phytomedicines are complex chemical mixtures prepared from plants. Water soluble phytoconstituents (flavonoids) are

poorly absorbed. Phytosome is novel drug delivery system is a patented technology that combines hydrophilic bioactive phyto-constituents of herbs/herbal extracts and bound by phospholipids. Phytosomes are one of the novel drug delivery system containing hydrophilic bioactive phyto-constituents of herbs surrounded and bounded by phospholipids. The phytosome technology produces a little microsphere or little cell, which protects the plant extract or its active constituent from destruction by gastric secretion and gut bacteria due to the gastro- protective property of Phosphatidyl choline [1-3].

The term "phyto" means plant while "some" means cell-like.

Fig-1-Structure of Phytosomes

Advantages

- More bioavailable than a simple/conventional herbal extract due to its enhanced capacity to cross the lipid rich bio-membranes and reach circulation.
- As they are better absorbed and produces better results
- Applied to standardized plant extracts, water soluble phyto-constituents and many popular herbal extracts including, grape seed, hawthorn, olive fruits and leaves, milk thistle, green tea, ginseng etc into phospholipids to produce lipid compatible molecular complex Polyphenolics and terpenes are ubiquitous in plants, but their poor solubility in water and organic solvents make the bioavailability of several botanical extracts erratic and poor.
- The limited solubility, both in water and in lipophilic phases, as well as hydrolytical instability at physiological pH values make several botanical extracts containing polyphenolics and terpenes very poorly absorbed both orally and topically.
- Bioavailability can be improved by using new delivery systems which can enhance the rate and

the extent of solubilization into aqueous intestinal fluids and the capacity to cross biomembranes.

TYPES AND CLASSIFICATION OF PHYTOSOMES:

Phytosomes are typically categorized based on the botanical extract they incorporate. Some common types include [4-5]:

1. Ginkgo Biloba Phytosome: Used for cognitive health and improving circulation.
2. Green Tea Phytosome: Often taken for its antioxidant properties and potential weight management benefits.
3. Milk Thistle Phytosome: Known for liver support and potential benefits in managing liver disorders.
4. Turmeric Phytosome (Curcumin Phytosome): Used for its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties.
5. Grape Seed Phytosome: Known for cardiovascular support due to its antioxidant content.
6. Bilberry Phytosome: Utilized for eye health and improving vision.

These phytosomes enhance the bioavailability of the botanical extracts, making them potentially more effective when compared to traditional formulations.

However, the specific benefits and effectiveness may vary based on individual health conditions. Always consult with a healthcare professional before incorporating phytosome supplements into your routine.

Phytosomes can be classified based on the type of plant extracts they incorporate and their intended applications. Common classifications include [6,7]:

1. Herbal Phytosomes: Contain extracts from medicinal plants or herbs, enhancing the absorption of active compounds.
2. Nutraceutical Phytosomes: Designed to improve the bioavailability of nutritional compounds, such as vitamins or antioxidants derived from plants.
3. Cosmeceutical Phytosomes: Used in skincare products to enhance the delivery and effectiveness of plant-derived compounds for skin health.
4. Anti-inflammatory Phytosomes: Incorporate plant extracts known for their anti-inflammatory properties, aiming to improve the therapeutic impact on inflammatory conditions.
5. Antioxidant Phytosomes: Focus on enhancing the absorption of antioxidants from plant sources to combat oxidative stress and support overall health.
6. Cardioprotective Phytosomes: Formulated to improve the absorption of plant extracts with cardio-protective properties, contributing to heart health.
7. The classification may vary based on specific formulations and the therapeutic or functional objectives of the phytosome product.

APPLICATION OF PHYTOSOMES [8-10]:

Silymarin phytosome:

Most of the phytosomes are focused to silybummarianum which contains premier ver-protectant flavanoids. The fruit of the milk thistle plant (*Silybum marianum*, family steraceae) contains flavanoids known for hepato-protective effects. Silymarin has been shown to have positive effects in treating liver diseases of various kinds, including hepatitis cirrhosis, fatty infiltration of the liver (chemical and alcohol induced fatty liver) and inflammation of the bile duct.

Phytosomes of grape seed

Grape seed phytosome is composed of oligomeric polyphenols of varying molecular size complexed with phospholipids. The main properties of polyphenols of grape seed are an increase in total antioxidant capacity and stimulation of physiological defenses of plasma.

Phytosome of green tea

Green tea leaves (*Camellia sinensis*) is characterized by presence of a polyphenolic compound epigallocatechin 3-O-gallate as the key component. These compounds are potent modulators of several biochemical processes linked to the breakdown of homeostasis in major chronic degenerative diseases such as cancer and atherosclerosis. Green tea also furnishes us with a number of beneficial activities such as antioxidant, anticarcinogenic, antimutagenic, hypocholesterolemic, cardio protective effects.

Phytosomes of curcumin

Maiti et al. developed the phytosomes of curcumin (flavonoid from turmeric, *Curcuma longa* Linn and naringenin (flavonoid from grape, *Vitis vinifera*).

Fig-2- Phytosomes for treatment of Corona Virus and Cancer Cells

PROPERTIES OF PHYTOSOMES [11-14]:**Biological Properties**

- Phytosomes are advanced forms of herbal products that are better absorbed, utilized and as a result produce better results than conventional herbal extracts. Freely soluble in non-polar and aprotic solvent, Solvents in which the hydrophilic moiety is not present.
- Moderately soluble in fats.
- Insoluble in water.
- Phytosomes can accommodate the active principle that is anchored to the polar head of the phospholipids, which finally becomes an integral part of the membrane.
- The increased bioavailability of the phytosome over the non complexed botanical derivatives has been demonstrated by pharmacokinetics studies or by pharmacodynamic tests in
- Experimental animals and in human subjects.

- Phytosomes are novel complexes that are better absorbed and utilized. Hence, they produce more bioavailability.

Chemical properties:

Phytosome is a complex between natural product and natural phospholipid.

The phytosome complex is obtained by reaction of suitable amount of phospholipid and the substrate in appropriate solvent such as glycerol.

The main phospholipid-substrate interaction is due to formation of hydrogen bonds between polar head of phospholipid and polar functionalities of substrate. When treated with water, they assume a micelle shape, forming structures which resembles liposomes.

Fig-3- Differences between Phytosomes and Liposomes

PREPARATION OF PHYTOSOMES [15-17]:

The preparation of phytosomes typically involves the following steps:

1. Selection of Extract: Choose a plant extract with therapeutic properties.
2. Selection of Phospholipid: Choose a suitable phospholipid, often phosphatidylcholine, to form the complex.
3. Hydration: Mix the plant extract with the phospholipid in a specific ratio and hydrate the mixture. This allows the phospholipids to surround the phytoconstituents.

4. Solvent Evaporation: Use a suitable solvent to dissolve excess phospholipids and then evaporate it, leaving behind the phytosome complex.
5. Drying: Dry the obtained phytosome complex to obtain a powder or suitable form for formulation.
6. Characterization: Perform characterization tests to ensure the quality and consistency of the phytosome product.

This method improves the bioavailability of plant constituents by enhancing their solubility and absorption. Keep in mind that specific details may vary depending on the targeted application and the characteristics of the plant extract used.

Fig-4-Method of Preparation of Phytosomes

CHARACTERISATIONS & EVALUATION OF PHYTOSOMES [17-20]:

Characterisations of Phytosomes:

The characterization of phytosomes involves various tests and analyses to ensure their quality, stability, and efficacy. Here are some common methods used for the characterization of phytosomes:

1. **Morphological Analysis:** Microscopic techniques, such as scanning electron microscopy (SEM) or transmission electron microscopy (TEM), are employed to examine the morphology and size distribution of phytosome particles.
2. **Particle Size Analysis:** Dynamic light scattering (DLS) or laser diffraction methods are used to measure the particle size distribution of phytosomes. This is crucial for understanding their bioavailability and dispersion properties.
3. **Zeta Potential Measurement:** Zeta potential provides information about the surface charge of phytosomes. This can influence their stability, as charged particles tend to repel each other, preventing aggregation.
4. **FTIR (Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy):** FTIR is used to analyze the functional groups present in the phytosome complex, confirming the successful formation of the complex and identifying potential chemical interactions.
5. **Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC):** DSC measures heat flow associated with thermal transitions, helping to assess the thermal behavior and stability of phytosome formulations.
6. **X-ray Diffraction (XRD):** XRD is employed to study the crystalline or amorphous nature of phytosomes, providing insights into their physical characteristics.
7. **HPLC (High-Performance Liquid Chromatography):** HPLC is used to quantify the content of specific phytoconstituents in the phytosome formulation, ensuring consistency and standardization.
8. **In vitro Release Studies:** Dissolution studies are conducted to assess the release profile of phytoconstituents from phytosomes, indicating their potential bioavailability.
9. **Stability Studies:** Long-term and accelerated stability studies are conducted to evaluate the shelf life and storage conditions of phytosome formulations.
10. **Characterization plays a crucial role in ensuring the reproducibility and quality of phytosome products, especially in the pharmaceutical and nutraceutical industries.**

Evaluation of Phytosomes:

Transition temperature:

The transition temperature of the vesicular lipid system can be settled via differential scanning calorimetry.

Entrapment efficiency:

The entrapment efficiency of a phytosomal preparation can be determined by exposing the preparation to ultracentrifugation method.

Vesicle size and zeta potential:

The particle size and zeta potential of phytosomes can be confirmed by dynamic light scattering, which usages a computerized examination system and photon correlation spectroscopy.

Surface tension activity measurement:

The surface tension activity of the drug in aqueous solution can be determined by the Du Nouy ring tensiometer.

Visualization:

Visualization of phytosomes can be accomplished using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and by transmission electron microscopy.

Vesicle stability:

The steadiness of vesicles can be measured by calculating the size and structure of the vesicles over time. The mean size is calculated by DLS and structural changes are monitored by fem.

Spectroscopic evaluation

To confirm the formation of a complex or to study the reciprocal interaction between the phytoconstituents and the phospholipid H1 NMR. C13 NMR. FTIR are used

In vitro and in vivo evaluations

Models of in-vitro and in-vivo evaluations are selected on the basis of the expected therapeutic activity phyto constituents present in the phytosome of biologically active compounds.

Features & Scope of Phytosomes:

Features of Phytosomes:

1. **Enhanced Bioavailability:** Phytosomes improve the absorption of bioactive compounds, increasing their availability to the body.
2. **Improved Stability:** The phospholipid complex provides stability to the plant extracts, protecting them from degradation.
3. **Targeted Delivery:** Phytosomes can be designed for targeted delivery of specific compounds to particular tissues or cells.
4. **Water Solubility:** They enhance the solubility of poorly water-soluble phytoconstituents, aiding in their absorption.
5. **Biological Activity:** Phytosomes often preserve the biological activity of the plant extracts, ensuring their therapeutic effects.

6. Versatility: Suitable for various applications, including herbal supplements, pharmaceuticals, and skincare products.
7. Reduced Dosages: Enhanced absorption allows for lower dosages while maintaining efficacy.
8. Synergistic Effects: Phytosomes may promote synergistic effects between the plant extracts and phospholipids, enhancing overall therapeutic outcomes.

Scope of phytosomes:

Scope of phytosomes is broad and includes various applications in the fields of medicine, nutrition, and skincare. Some key aspects of the scope of phytosomes include:

1. Nutritional Supplements: Phytosomes are used to enhance the bioavailability of dietary supplements, ensuring better absorption of essential nutrients.
2. Herbal Medicine: In herbal medicine, phytosomes improve the delivery and effectiveness of plant extracts, making them more potent and reliable.
3. Pharmaceuticals: Phytosomes are explored in pharmaceutical formulations to improve the absorption and therapeutic outcomes of certain drugs.
4. Skincare Products: Phytosomes find application in skincare formulations, promoting the efficient delivery of bioactive compounds for improved skin health.
5. Targeted Drug Delivery: The ability to design phytosomes for targeted delivery makes them promising for precision medicine, where specific tissues or cells can be targeted with therapeutic compounds.
6. Bioavailability Enhancement: The primary role of phytosomes is to enhance the bioavailability of poorly soluble compounds, which is beneficial across various industries.
7. Research and Development: Ongoing research explores new possibilities and applications for phytosomes, expanding their scope in medical and wellness-related fields.
8. Reduced Side Effects: By improving absorption and targeted delivery, phytosomes may contribute to reducing side effects associated with certain compounds.

CONCLUSION:

Phytosomes are newly introduced technology in drug delivery. It is being applied to phyto constituents for the improvement of bioavailability of herbal drug. Phytosomes have both properties like pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics and have wide range of cosmeticology. But this technology is

not limited to polyphenolic alkaloids. Phytosomal formulations are simple and reproducible as a part of that phospholipid but also help to increase the therapeutic value by reducing toxicity and increasing the bioavailability and so on. Recently, pharmaceutical scientists have shifted their focus to designing a drug delivery system for herbal medicines using a scientific approach. The novel research can also aid in capturing as well as to remain in the market. But there are many challenges with herbal drugs which need to be overcome like difficulty of conducting clinical research in herbal drugs, development of simple bioassays for biological standardization, pharmacological and toxicological evaluation methods' development, investigation of their sites of absorption, toxic herbal drugs in use, discovering various animal models for toxicity and safety evaluation, legal and regulatory aspects of herbal drugs and so on.

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